

Studies on Adsorption Indicators II. Substituted Dibromo-tetrachlorophthalides in Argentometric Titrations*

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Suitability of two new substituted dibromo-tetrachlorophthalides as adsorption indicators in Argentometric titrations of halide and thiocyanate ions has been studied. The 3-methyl-3-(3',5'-dibromo-2',4'-dihydroxyphenyl)4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide (I) and 3-phenyl-3-(3',5'-dibromo-2',4'-dihydroxyphenyl)4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide (II) can be used in Argentometric titrations. Detailed experimental procedures have been described for I and II.

EOSIN or 2', 4', 5', 7'-tetrabromo-fluorescein is a well known adsorption indicator in Argentometric titrations of halides. Dibromoresorcinol succinein and tetrabromoresorcinol succinein have also been reported in literature¹ to be useful as adsorption indicators for the same purpose.

In a previous communication³ the present authors have shown that behaviour of 3-substituted phthalides is difficult to understand on the basis of the existing theories (Fajans², Kolthoff⁴) of adsorption indicators. It was, therefore, thought desirable to extend the studies to 3-substituted dibromo-tetrachlorophthalides.

Results and Discussions

The absorptivity and colour changes of dyes I and II have been compared with Eosin as follows:

3-Methyl-3-(3', 5'-dibromo-2', 4'-dihydroxyphenyl) 4, 5, 6, 7-tetrachlorophthalide (I): Adsorbility good;

titration possible for Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , and CNS^- . Suspension (Cl^- , pink tinged-white; Br^- , yellow; I^- , yellow; CNS^- , buff) $\longrightarrow$ pink ppt.

3-Phenyl-3-(3', 5'-dibromo-2', 4'-dihydroxyphenyl) 4, 5, 6, 7-tetrachlorophthalide (II): Adsorbility slighter than I; titration possible for Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , and CNS^- . Suspension (Cl^- , white; Br^- , yellowish-white; I^- , yellow; CNS^- , pink tinged-white) $\longrightarrow$ pink ppt.

Eosin (2', 4', 5', 7'-tetrabromo-fluorescein): Adsorbility good; titration possible in neutral and acidic medium (5 ml 6N AcOH) for halides and thiocyanate ions, with solutions ranging from 0.1N to 0.01N dilution. Suspension (Cl^- , pink tinged-white to light pink; Br^- , yellow-orange to light orange; I^- , yellow to light orange; CNS^- , pinkish-buff to light pink) $\longrightarrow$ bright pink ppt.

The absorption maxima of Eosin and the above dyes (I and II) are almost the same but there is variation in adsorbility and the order is Eosin > I > II. Here, also the halogen (Cl^-) substitution in the acid part of the dye molecule evidently decreases adsorbility to some extent in I and II, and the results

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TABLE—DYES I AND II USED AS ADSORPTION INDICATORS. VOLUME OF HALIDE AND THIOCYANATE TAKEN FOR TITRATION: 10 ML; DROPS OF INDICATOR USED: 8 DROPS IN NEUTRAL OR ACIDIC MEDIUM. (CONCN. STANDS FOR CONCENTRATION, AND PPT. FOR PRECIPITATE).

Dye used	Concn. of solution	Volume and concn. of AgNO ₃ used	Transition of colour	Remarks
I	0.1N NaCl	10.02 ml 0.1 N	white suspn. (pink tinged) → Pink ppt.	Coagulation starts 2 drops before the end point but at the end point the suspn. attains light pink colour and coagulates completely; the end point is sharp.
I	0.02N NaCl (5 ml 6N AcOH)	10.02 ml 0.02 N	white suspn. (pink tinged) → pink ppt.	Coagulation starts before the end point, but the whole of the ppt. coagulates at the end point leaving clear supernatant liquid (In neutral medium, coagulation takes place at the end point).
I	0.1N KBr (3 ml 6N AcOH)	10.00 ml 0.1 N	yellow suspn. → pink ppt.	Coagulation starts before the end point, but at the end point light red colour develops and whole of the ppt. coagulates leaving clear supernatant liquid (In neutral medium coagulation takes place at the end point).
I	0.02N KBr (3 ml 6N AcOH)	10.02 ml 0.02 N	yellow-white suspn. → pink ppt.	Same as with 0.1N KBr.
I	0.1N KI	10.00 ml 0.1 N	yellow suspn → yellow-pink ppt.	Coagulation takes place at the end point; the colour change at the end point is light pink.
I	0.02N KI	10.00 ml 0.02 N	orange-yellow suspn. → pink ppt.	the suspn. attains sharp light pink colour and coagulates completely.
I	0.004N KI	10.00 ml 0.004N	orange-yellow suspn. → pink ppt.	the solution attains orange-pink colour at the end point, and coagulates after shaking well.
I	0.1N KCNS	10.00 ml 0.1 N	buff suspn. → pink ppt.	Coagulation starts before the end point, but at the end point the suspn. attains light pink colour and coagulates completely (In acidic medium the behaviour is the same).
I	0.02N KCNS	10.00 ml 0.02 N	light pink suspn. → pink ppt.	Coagulation takes place at the end point.
II	0.1N NaCl	10.00 ml 0.1 N	white suspn. → pink ppt.	coagulation takes place at the end point; the suspn. attains light pink colour at the end point and coagulated completely.
II	0.02N NaCl (2 ml 6N AcOH)	10.02 ml 0.02 N	white suspn. → pink ppt.	same as with 0.1N NaCl.
II	0.1N KBr	10.00 ml 0.1 N	yellow white suspn. → pink ppt.	coagulation takes place at the end point; suspn. attains light pink colour at the end point.
II	0.02N KBr (3 ml 6N AcOH)	10.02 ml 0.02 N	yellow-white suspn. → pink-yellow ppt.	coagulation takes place at the end point; suspn. attain very light pink colour at the end point.
II	0.1N KI	10.00 ml 0.1 N	yellow suspn. → pink-yellow ppt.	coagulation starts 3 drops before the end point, but at the end point the suspn. develops light red colour and coagulates completely.
II	0.02N KI	10.00 ml 0.02 N	yellow suspn. → orange-pink ppt.	coagulation takes place at the end point; the end point colour change of the suspn. is not sharp.
II	0.01N KI	10.02 ml 0.01 N	yellow suspn. → pink ppt.	coagulation takes place at the end point.
II	0.1N KCNS	10.00 ml 0.1 N	white suspn. (pink tinged) → pink ppt.	coagulation starts before the end point, but at the end point whole of the ppt. coagulates leaving clear supernatant liquid.
II	0.02N KCNS	10.00 ml 0.02 N	white suspn. (pink tinged) → pink ppt.	coagulation takes place at the end point; the suspn. develops light pink colour at the end point.
II	0.01N KCNS	10.00 ml 0.01 N	faint-pink suspn. → pink ppt.	the suspn. develops more pronounced pink colour towards the end point and coagulates after shaking well.

partly agree with Fajans² views. But the adsorbability also seems to depend on 3-substituted CH_3 and C_6H_5 groups in I and II respectively.

Experimental

Materials : See³.

Indicator Solutions : A 0.2% solution of the dye was prepared in rectified spirit.

Preparation of the dyes : The necessary acids, *o*-acetyltetrachlorobenzoic acid⁵, and *o*-benzoyltetrachlorobenzoic acid⁶ were prepared by standard methods and then condensed with resorcinol to obtain the resorcinol dyes (Unsymmetric or mixed phthaleins) which on bromination resulted in the formation of 3-methyl-3-(3', 5'-dibromo-2', 4'-dihydroxyphenyl)4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide⁷ (I) and 3-phenyl-3-(3', 5'-dibromo-2', 4'-dihydroxyphenyl) 4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide⁷ (II) respectively. Detailed observations on both the above dibromo dyes as adsorption indicators are given in the following table.

The following points emerge on comparing the above adsorption indicators I and II (In acidic medium coagulation starts before the end point, but the pink ppt. coagulates completely at the end point).

1. *Titration of Chloride Ions against Silver Ions* : With dyes I and II, the titrations can be better done with 0.1*N* solutions. With 0.02*N* solutions the end points are not sharp, but coagulation takes place at the end point. The titrations are possible in neutral and acidic medium. With 0.01*N* dilutions the end points are not also sharp, but complete coagulation of the ppt. takes place at the end point.

2. *Titration of Bromide Ions against Silver Ions* : With dyes I and II, the titrations can be better done

with 0.1*N* solutions in neutral or acidic medium. With 0.02*N* solutions, I shows very light pink colour at the end point, but the pink ppt. coagulates completely; II does not give indication of colour change at the end point, but the pink-yellow ppt. coagulates completely at the end point. Titrations are possible in neutral and acidic medium.

3. *Titration of Iodide Ions against Silver Ions* : With dyes I and II, the titrations can be better done with 0.1*N* and 0.05*N* solutions in neutral medium. Dyes I and II, with 0.02*N* and 0.01*N* solutions show light colour change, and no sharp colour change respectively; but the coagulation of the ppt. is complete (generally with shaking) at the end point. Neutral medium seems to be better for the end points.

4. *Titration of Thiocyanate Ions against Silver Ions* : With dyes I and II, the titrations can be done with 0.1*N* and 0.05*N* solutions in neutral or acidic medium. With 0.01*N* solution, the pink ppt. coagulates at the end point, but I requires much shaking.

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